

SEMANTIC PECULIARITIES OF EXPRESSIONS MADE WITH THE VERB "أتى" ("TO COME") IN ARABIC

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Annotation: This article examines the category of the verb word in the Arabic language and its study by linguists, lexico-semantic analysis of the verb “to come” "أتى" from action verbs. The article explains what meanings the action verb “to come” "أتى" acquires in the Arabic explanatory dictionary, as well as what semantic changes this verb undergoes when it comes with prepositions. It can be seen that there is a significant difference between the number of meanings of these verbs given in the explanatory dictionaries of the Arabic language.

Key words: verb category, verb tenses, verb semantics, Arabic and Uzbek linguistics, study of this topic by Arab scholars, works.

INTRODUCTION

The verb “to come” can also be part of phraseological expressions of the language, and the use of this verb in phraseological expressions of the Arabic language has been compared and their similarities and differences have been revealed. Currently, a lot of research is being conducted in world linguistics.. However, in Arabic linguistics, scientists mostly adhere to the traditional approach to the verb category and study it morphologically.

In Arabic, verbs expressing human behavior make up a large part of the lexicon of this language. Since this group of verbs is one of the topics currently being studied in Arabic linguistics, it is important to study them.

METHODOLOGY

In this article, the verb of action in the Uzbek language corresponds in content to the lexeme of advent in the Arabic language. When expressing some of the meanings inherent in the Uzbek verb “to come”, it is the Arabic alternative that should be used. In some cases, the meaning of this action verb in Uzbek is expressed both in Arabic and in the verb “to come”, however, in this case it is necessary to choose exactly the verb that expresses the expected meaning from synonymous verbs meaning “to come” in Arabic. In the article, this situation is explained by examples.

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

In Arabic linguistics, since the 8th century, books related to the study of the verb family have been written, and such research works are still ongoing. The works of classical Arabic linguists Sibawayhi, Ibn Sarraj, Zajjaji, Zamakhshari, Ibn Ya'ish, Abu Hayyan, and modern linguists Muhammad Dawood, Ahmed Berissul, Abdul Qadir Husayn can be included in this category. The above-mentioned linguists' definitions of the verb reflect the general meaning that "a verb is a word that expresses time and action." Also, one of the mature scholars of Arabic puberty science, Abdul Mutaadiys Saidi, as-Sayed Ahmad al-Hashimi, Shavqi Saiflar, the place of the verb in Arabic grammar and sentence construction, its specific aspects in its use, verb weights , definite and passive adjectives formed from verbs, learned the names of places and weapons.

In the works of linguists on the study of the verb phraseology in the Arabic language, a traditional approach to this topic is observed, and it can be seen that the verb is studied more morphologically in these works. However, in the history of Arabic linguistics, it should be noted that there are several works in which the semantics of the lexical layer of the Arabic language are studied in general, although not specifically within the framework of the verb group. Sibawayhi's "al-

Kitab", Ibn Durayd's "Jamharat al-lug'a", Ismail al-Jawhari's "al-Sihhah", Ibn Jinni's "al-Khasais", Ibn Faris's "al-Sahib", Saalibi's "Fiqh al-lug" 'a wa asraar al-I'raabiyah", al-Firuzabadi's works "al-Qamus al-Muhiyt" also touched on issues such as semantic peculiarities of words, homonymy and synonymy in the Arabic language.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The topics related to the semantic classification of verbs in Arabic language are one of the areas that are currently being studied in linguistics, and when you closely familiarize yourself with the existing works, it is known that most of them are related to the study of the semantics of verbs found in the Holy Qur'an. happened, the most prominent of the research works in this regard is the book "بريهي شياع الثويني by " في السياق القراني حرف الأف" دلالاتها في السياق القراني حرف الأف". In this work, the scientist studied the meanings of all the verbs beginning with the letter "alif" in the Holy Qur'an, and explained 16 semantic meanings of the verb¹ "أتى " "to come" from the verbs of action. "Kelmoq" in the Uzbek language is one of the lexemes expressing the concept of action. 14 different meanings of this lexeme are expressed in the "Uzbek language explanatory dictionary" of the verb to come².

"معجم المعاني الجامع" in the explanatory dictionary, 24 meanings of the action verb to come are expressed³. There is a noticeable difference between the number of meanings of these verbs given in the explanatory dictionaries of both languages. In "Uzbek-Arabic As-Sultan Dictionary" more than 15 meanings of the verb to come are presented with examples.⁴ 17 meanings of the action verb

¹ دكتور بريهي شياع الثويني "افعال في القرآن الكريم و دلالاتها في السياق القراني حرف الاف"

² O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati.-M.: Rus tili.-1981.-1j.

³ معجم المعاني الجامع

⁴ "O'zbekcha-arabcha As-Sulton lug'ati", "Hilol nashr" MCHJ nashriyoti, Toshkent-2011

"come" are given in the Arabic-Uzbek dictionary “النعيم-An-na'im”⁵, which includes almost all layers of the lexicon of the modern Arabic literary language.

According to the semantic classification of the Arabic verb "come", it belongs to the group of verbs that express an orderly action carried out in a certain direction, and in the electronic annotated dictionary "معجم المعاني الجامع" there are 24 meanings of this verb given⁶ The meanings of the verb "to come" can be divided into the following groups based on factors such as the subject performing the action, the means of its execution, and the intended goal:

1. The verb "to come" and its synonyms, expressing the action of a person in a certain direction. These verbs differ from each other in the means of performing the action ("جاء" - the action is performed with the feet, "وصل" - the action is performed in a vehicle), the intended goal ("ورد" - the action is performed according to the suggestion, - coming in order to reserve water) differs in aspects such as

2. Represents the beginning of an event or the period set for it (in the sense of the verb "حلّ"):

سوف يأتي يوم الحساب آجلاً أو عاجلاً

3. Transition from one state to another represents rotation:

■ "اذهّبوا بقميصي هذا فالقوه على وجه أبي يأت بصيراً"⁸

4. Represents intimacy with a woman:

■ فإذا تطهرن فأتوهن من حيث أمركم الله

5. "أتى" the meaning of the verb is to present something to someone:

Actually, this verb is intransitive"ب" when accompanied by a

⁵ “النعيم-An-na'im” arabcha-o'zbekcha lug'ati, Tashkent-2003

⁶ <https://www.almaany.com/ar/dict/ar-ar//أتى>

⁷ <https://www.almaany.com/ar/dict/ar-ar//أتى>

preposition, it is used in the sense of making someone or something present "أحضر" or "فاعل" when it comes to weight, it becomes a transitive verb and is used in the sense of making someone or something present "أعطى"، "أحضر" expresses the specific meanings of verbs:

- آتاه الله رزق عميماً: أعطاه
- آتاه النعم : ساقها إليه
- آتاه غداءه : أتى به إليه
- أتى بالبينة الواضحة⁹

Also, "أتى" verb by participating in the creation of some jurisprudential expressions with the participation of such words "مال", "زكاة", expresses its meaning "أعطى"، "أدى":

- أتى الزكاة : أداها
- أتى الصلاة دباراً
- أتى المال¹⁰

"أتى" verb , if it comes with the preposition "على" in weight "فاعل", it is "وافق"، "جارى أحدا في شيء"، "طالع" can be synonymous with verbs:

- آتاه على الأمر¹¹

6. "أتى" verb can be synonymous with verbs "دمر"، "هدم":

If the verb "أتى" fe'lining if it is used in speech, it can be seen that in the semantics of this verb, which preposition it comes with is also important. Above is its with prepositions "ب" and "على" the cases that have come show this. when it comes with the preposition "على" of this verb, it means to destroy, to wipe out:

- أتى الحريق على الأخضر و اليابس

This is the verb "على" in the Holy Qur'an it can be seen that it comes in the

⁹ <https://www.almaany.com/ar/dict/ar-ar//أتى/>

¹⁰ <https://www.almaany.com/ar/dict/ar-ar//أتى/>

¹¹ <https://www.almaany.com/ar/dict/ar-ar//أتى/>

same sense without the presence of a preposition:

- Nahl, 26.

7. "أتى" verb with this preposition "ب" when used together or alone, means to do something, to do, to do something:

- أتى بالقادورة
- أتى بمنكر فاحش
- أتى بعمل خبيث
- أتى البهتان
- أتى فعلا فاحشا
- أتى رجا¹²

Pay attention to the structure of these sentences, the verb "أتى" , it can be seen that it expresses the meaning of "to do" mainly when it comes with nouns with a negative connotation.

8. "أتى" he verb comes in the meaning of "to speak", its use in this sense is more common in phrases, with preposition "ب" they came together observed:

- أتى بالقول الفصل
- أتى بعوراء (أتى بكلمة شنيعة)
- أتى بكلام عويص

9. Came in this phrase¹³ أتى الأمر - verb "أتى" can be synonym with these verbs "قرب" va "دنا", "حان" .

¹⁴ - Surah Nahl, verse 1 "أتى أمر الله فلا تستعجلوه " أي أنت ساعته

10. "أتى" verb used figuratively:

"أتى بطم" expression is used to express that a person is very surprised.

"أتى بناموس عجيب" the phrase is used to express a person's resourcefulness.

¹² " معجم المعاني الجامع "

¹³ " معجم المعاني الجامع "

¹⁴ Alouddin Mansur. Qur'oni Karim. – Toshkent : « Cho'lpon », 1992

11. أتي بعتب¹⁵ – scold

بنقص وفساد – to blame (to talk about someone's shortcomings and immorality)

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, there are similarities and differences in the expression of the Uzbek verb "to come" in Arabic. In the Uzbek language, the main form of this action verb looks rather simple, but in content it corresponds to the lexeme of the Arabic language "to come". In the Uzbek language, this verb requires the object to be addressed, mainly in terms of arrival, place-time, exit, and departure, while in Arabic, they are expressed by a preposition that gives the meaning of the arrival agreement or a specific agreement. When expressing some meanings specific to the Uzbek verb "to come", it is necessary to use their Arabic alternative, and in some cases, the meanings of this action verb in the Uzbek language in Arabic, it is expressed by the verb "to come", but in this case, it is necessary to choose exactly one verb that expresses the expected meaning from the synonymous verbs that give the meaning of "to come".

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